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The role of social media influencers and eWOM in driving purchase intention: insights from SMEs in the gamarra cluster

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of social media influencers (SMI) and electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) on purchase intention (PI) within small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) agglomerated in the Gamarra textile cluster in Lima, Peru. Grounded in cluster theory and source credibility theory, the research aims to understand how these digital marketing strategies shape cluster-level brand trust (BT) and consumer brand engagement (CBE), ultimately influencing customer purchase decisions in one of the clustered SEMs. Data were collected via an online survey of 395 followers who engage with influencers frequently posting content related to the cluster. Using partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM), the study confirms that both SMI and eWOM positively affect BT and CBE, although SMI has a stronger impact on CBE than eWOM. Additionally, CBE was found to be a more significant driver of PI than BT, reinforcing its role as a key construct in digital marketing effectiveness. The findings contribute theoretically by extending the application of source credibility and cluster theories to the context of agglomerated SMEs using shared branding. Practically, the study suggests that cluster managers should prioritise influencer-based strategies to build engagement and trust, especially when marketing budgets are limited. These insights offer actionable guidance for SMEs seeking to compete more effectively through clustering digital branding initiatives.

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1. Introduction

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) represent 99% of the enterprise population and are integral to national economies, particularly pronounced in developing countries, where SMEs dominate a substantial portion of business sectors (OECD, 2023); the reason why academically, numerous scholars advocate for the study of SMEs rather than large corporations due to their significance in employment and the economy. In recent years, it has become widely recognised that SMEs are undergoing significant digital transformations to remain competitive in the currently complex and global environment (OECD, 2023). Marketing strategies are at the forefront of the digital transformation of SMEs, with the adoption of digital marketing practices becoming increasingly widespread despite the varied outcomes (Jadhav et al., 2023). Although prior research on SMEs has demonstrated that the adoption of Internet marketing strategies facilitates steady growth (Ali Abbasi et al., 2022; Sharabati et al., 2024) since it enables these entities to thrive in increasingly competitive and complex markets (Jadhav et al., 2023), SMEs face limitations attributed to a lack of knowledge regarding digital marketing and its potential benefits, which is often linked to their limited size, lack of digital competences and insufficient resources to invest in and implement digital transformation strategies (Appio et al., 2024; Chatterjee & Kumar Kar, 2020).

The Peruvian textile sector serves as a pertinent example of a lack of marketing and sales capabilities, as noted by the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) (Beverinotti et al., 2023), especially those SMEs agglomerated at the renowned Gamarra cluster, situated in Lima, Peru, where approximately 30.000 SMEs

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converge to produce and sell textiles and garments, generating annual sales of \$1,166 million. (Instituto Nacional de Informática y Estadística (INEI), 2019).

The OECD (2023) identified networking, and particularly clustering, as one of the most comprehensive and optimal strategies for SMEs to manage digital transformation by facilitating the sharing of common objectives, information, or costs. This study, situated within the context of Gamarra—a prominent example of an agglomerate economy—aims to investigate the impact of two prevalent Internet marketing strategies, namely electronic word of mouth (eWOM) and social media influencers (SMI) associated with the cluster's brand, on customer attitudes and perceptions of the cluster's brand. Ultimately, this research seeks to determine how these Internet marketing strategies and the cluster's brand factors influence customer purchase intention (PI) for products offered by the clustered SMEs.

Two theories are applied to support this research: Cluster and Sourcer Credibility theories. Cluster Theory posits that a cluster is a group of geographically neighbouring interconnected companies and related organisations operating in a certain area, characterised by common activities and complementary to each other (Delgado et al., 2010; Porter & Kramer, 2006). According to this theory, if a cluster collectively implements marketing strategies rather than each SME doing so individually, it can be advantageous for the SMEs within the cluster (Felzensztein & Deans, 2013). As Devigili et al. (2018) asserted, consumers often attribute the benefits and strengths of a cluster brand to its individual members. Consequently, in the context of Gamarra, the SMEs can leverage the cluster's brand Internet marketing strategies to enhance their own sales.

Moreover, the source credibility theory (Hovland et al., 1953; Ohanian, 1990) theorises that the persuasiveness of the message depends on the perceived expertise, trustworthiness, and attractiveness of sources such as SMI or eWOM. In this context, SMI and eWOM strongly influence customer attitudes and behaviours, and previous investigations have confirmed in different sectors that SMI and eWOM have the ability to generate greater identification and brand trust (BT) in users (Castelló Martínez & del Pino Romero, 1970; Ebrahim, 2020; Leite & Baptista, 2022; Wang & Chan-Olmsted, 2024), as well as customer brand engagement (CBE) due to its capacity to influence online customer behaviour (Delbaere et al., 2021; Hollebeek et al., 2016; Ngarmwongnoi et al., 2020).

Despite the acknowledged significance of SMI and eWOM in contemporary marketing strategies, a research gap remains, as these variables have been inadequately examined within the SME sector (Ahmad et al., 2018; Striedinger Meléndez, 2018) and have not been addressed in the cluster literature until now. In this sense, this study sheds light on the importance of SMI and eWOM associated with the cluster's brand on the cluster's BT and CBE, ultimately determining the customer purchase intention (PI) for the products offered by the small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within the cluster.

Methodologically, considering the factors previously discussed and the assertion that SMI represents a multidimensional construct, the study used a second-order structural equation modelling approach using partial least squares (PLS-SEM) and calculated $PLS_{predict}$ to assess the model's predictive power beyond the sample. This approach aligns with recent recommendations for evaluating prediction in marketing models (Shmueli et al., 2019). The study population consisted of potential clients of one of the SMEs agglomerated in Gamarra, considering that most of the clients of the cluster are women who follow influencers who create regular content about the cluster. Using the CAWI approach, the authors asked three influencers to share an online questionnaire with their followers through social media, such as Facebook, Instagram or TikTok, to collect the data.

This article is structured as follows: The objectives and relevance of this study are justified in the introduction. The literature review discusses the roots of each hypothesis. The following section explains the sampling technique, data collection procedure, scales used, and PLS-SEM approach. The results are presented in the fourth section. The discussion is used to compare our results with previous literature and to suggest theoretical and practical implications. The article ends with a proposal for future research and an explanation of the limitations of the study.

2. Literature review and hypotheses

This section, grounded in the cluster and source credibility theories, elucidates the background of the constructs incorporated into the proposed empirical model, specifically SMI, eWOM, BT, CBE, and PI.

Furthermore, within the framework of PLS-SEM, eight hypotheses are posited, predicated on the premise that SMI and eWOM are pivotal variables in Internet marketing, capable of generating BT and CBE, particularly within a cluster, and influencing the PI of potential clients of agglomerated SMEs. Additionally, the hypotheses suggest a relationship between the cluster's BT and CBE and the PI of each SME integrated within the cluster.

2.1. eWOM

The source credibility theory is frequently employed to elucidate the effectiveness of messages in both online and offline contexts. However, eWOM from anonymous consumers may occasionally diminish readers' confidence in interpreting review content sources (Hsieh & Li, 2020). This underscores the necessity of comprehending how consumers evaluate the eWOM and influence their attitudes and behaviours. The concept of word of mouth (WOM) was conceptualised as a consumer behaviour in which information about a purchase is shared (Dichter, 1966) with family and friends. Over time, the concept of WOM began to be related to the electronic context and was named eWOM, which was defined as a statement made by potential or real customers about a product or company in a digital context (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004) or based on the source credibility theory as "the extent to which one perceives other consumers' recommendations or reviews as believable, true, or factual" (Levy & Gvili, 2015). In the specific case of the clusters, although the eWOM has not been analysed in depth, some research on SMEs has confirmed the effect of this variable on improving Communication with customers (Konstantopoulou et al., 2019) and the company's competitiveness (Serra Cantallops & Salvi, 2014).

Regarding the relationships among eWOM with BT, PI, and CBE, a limited number of researchers have considered the relationship between these constructs. For eWOM and CBE, even though the number of previous studies is scarce, Srivastava and Sivaramakrishnan (2021) and Yoo et al. (2013) confirmed the relationship between both constructs. Additionally, previous studies have found that eWOM influences consumer PI in sectors such as B2B (Serra Cantallops & Salvi, 2014; Verma et al., 2023). In the case of how eWOM impacts BT, even Commitment-Trust Theory (Morgan & Hunt, 1994) postulates that brand communications, and by extension, eWOM, since it is one of the most potent and trustworthy communication channels, is an antecedent of brand trust, and the amount of empirical research that confirms the relationship is limited. Some studies have included eWOM as a dimension of Social Media Marketing (Sohaib & Han, 2023; Vrontis et al., 2021). Meanwhile, few studies have proved the influence of eWOM on BT (Kumar et al., 2023; Majeed et al., 2023) or brand trust change (Seifert & Kwon, 2019), and none related to clusters. Nevertheless, based on previous research and cluster and customer engagement theories, the following statements are proposed:

- H1:** EWOM about the cluster positively influences the cluster's CBE.
- H2:** EWOM about the cluster positively influences the PI of products sold by the cluster's SMEs.
- H3:** EWOM about the cluster positively influences the cluster's BT.

2.2. Social media influencer (SMI)

According to source credibility theory (Hovland et al., 1953), the perceived credibility of one source, as an example of an influence, depends on the perceived expertise, trustworthiness, and attractiveness of its source and conditioned the persuasiveness of the messages shared by the source (Hovland et al., 1953; Lou & Yuan, 2019a) and affect the credibility of the original message (Martínez-López et al., 2020). Throughout marketing history, influencers have been used to promote brands and products. In this sense, initially, influencers were seen as people who had a high standard of living (Booth & Matic, 2011), but with the appearance of digital media, such as websites and social media platforms, other types of influencers emerged. Digital influencers, commonly referred to as social media influencers (SMI), play a crucial role in contemporary online brand communication, as their credibility can

significantly influence the brand attitudes of their followers (Dangi & Dhun, 2023; Van Reijmersdal et al., 2024).

As previously indicated, the main attraction of SMIs lies in their ability to involve their followers in experiences actively (Joshi et al., 2023; Lou & Yuan, 2019); this is the reason why companies seek to identify the ideal SMI for their target audience to motivate the PI of their products and positively affect BT (Ebrahim, 2020; von Mettenheim & Wiedmann, 2021; Wiedmann & von Mettenheim, 2020b). On the other hand, SMIs have also been proven as one of the primary constructs for generating positive CBE for brands (Hollebeek, 2011; Tafheem et al., 2021; Vinerean & Opreana, 2021). Furthermore, in SMI literature, there is evidence that the influencer spreads influential opinions about brands, services, and products that the follower desires. Hence, an influencer's credibility is projected in products, services, or BT (Wiedmann & von Mettenheim, 2020a), which impacts consumer engagement and promotes future purchases (Sharma et al., 2020). Although these relationships have been studied in marketing, their study of agglomerate industries is not widespread. Moreover, based on the review of Vrontis et al. (2021) regarding the SMI and its relationship with BT and CBE, we hypothesised that the SMI focus on the cluster can positively influence its CBE and BT. Moreover, we propose that the cluster's SMI affects the PI of the products sold by the cluster's SMEs. In line with the previous findings, the following hypotheses are postulated:

- H4:** The cluster SMI positively influences the cluster CBE.
- H5:** Cluster SMI positively influences the PI of products sold by cluster SMEs.
- H6:** The cluster SMI positively influences the cluster BT.

2.3. Brand trust (BT)

Brand Trust (BT) is defined as the consumer's will to perform a previously declared function, mainly when there is high uncertainty regarding a brand or product (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001; Doney & Cannon, 1997). For this reason, BT is essential for SMEs because it allows consumers to perceive the brand as consistent and, therefore, establish a link with it.

According to some studies, BT is related to some variables, such as brand loyalty (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001; Laroche et al., 2013) or brand value (Delgado-Ballester & Munuera-Alemán, 2005). Similarly, BT has been studied in the SME sector because of its importance in the company's growth, its relationship with brand loyalty, and the impact of BT on PI in SMEs (Alonso Dos Santos et al., 2022; Lude & Prügl, 2018). Apart from the importance of the influence of BT on CBE, which was proven in sectors such as e-commerce (Jain et al., 2019; Jibril et al., 2019) and luxury (Husain et al., 2022), apparently no relevant investigations have studied this relationship in a conglomerate context. Nevertheless, based on previous research, the authors presume that the cluster's BT can be considered an antecedent of the PI of the products sold by SMEs agglomerated in the cluster, and the following hypotheses are posited:

- H7:** Cluster BT positively influences the PI of the products sold by cluster SMEs by potential customers.

2.4. Consumer brand engagement (CBE)

Consumer Brand Engagement (CBE) is a psychological process that occurs through an interactive and creative customer experience with a brand (Brodie et al., 2011). This concept gained ground among various academics, thus fitting within the broader theoretical perspectives of dominant service logic (Vargo & Lusch, 2008, 2016) which emphasises value co-creation through collaborative and dynamic interactions between firms and customers. Additionally, it resonates with relational marketing (Vivek et al., 2012), which prioritises the development of long-term relationships. In the context of digital marketing, consumers have the opportunity to interact with brands or co-create content, rendering CBE essential for fostering stable relationships.

Given its importance and novelty, CBE has been studied in a broad range of sectors. Previous investigations have proven that highly engaged consumers generate more income for SMEs (Lăzăroiu et al., 2020) by increasing their average spending, the frequency with which consumers buy (Barger et al.,

2016), improving the lifetime of the consumer, reducing the cost of acquiring new customers, and generating PI (Bianchi & Andrews, 2018; Tseng et al., 2021a). Nevertheless, it should be noted that, in the SMEs or cluster sectors, despite its growing importance and the fact that the customer engagement theory (Pansari & Kumar, 2017) and the branding process (Loureiro, 2023) postulates the existence of the relationship, the study of the link between CBE and PI is still limited (Alkhasoneh et al., 2025). Nevertheless, as it was previously explained, this research has the objective of probing whether the cluster's CBE can benefit the SMEs that integrate the conglomerate and impulse their sales through the PI of the potential customers, and aiming to shed more light on the cluster and customer brand engagement literature, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H8: Cluster CBE positively influences the PI of the products sold by cluster SMEs by potential customers.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Sampling approach

The study population comprised potential clients of one of the small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) located within Gamarra, the largest agglomerated cluster in South America. This cluster, situated in Lima, Peru, hosts over 30,000 SMEs engaged in the production and sale of garments and textiles. Within this cluster, the majority of clients are women, many of whom follow influencers who frequently post messages on social media regarding Gamarra. Data were collected in September 2022 through an online self-administered survey using a snowball sampling technique. To avoid sampling bias, three influencers, each with followers ranging from 1,000 to 10,000 and who consistently posted content almost exclusively about Gamarra, collaborated with the authors to disseminate an online questionnaire among their followers. The followers, predominantly women aged 18–50, were reached via social media platforms used by the three influencers, such as Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok, through different posts in which the three influencers requested their followers to participate in the research. All participants in the research were asked for their written informed consent statement to collect and process the data, and no confidential or individual information to identify them was asked. Moreover, this investigation was conducted according to the Declaration of Helsinki and under the ethical code for scientific research approved by the Peruvian University of Applied Sciences' ethical committee (INV-COD-01). Additionally, the Peruvian Law to Protect Personal Information "Ley N° 29733" and the Decreto Supremo N°003-2013-JUS were considered during this research.

The questionnaire was structured to mitigate common method bias (Kock et al., 2021) and was divided into two parts. The first section was used to obtain information on the sample's sociodemographic profile (see Table 1). The final sample comprised 395 participants. 89.7% were female, 9.8% were male, and 0.5% were non-binary. The age range was distributed—18–23 years (31%), 24–29 years, 30–35 years (19.8%), and the rest (8.9%). Moreover, 45.8% of the sample only worked, 28.4% worked and studied, and the rest of the sample was unemployed or retired. Finally, Instagram was the first social network used by followers (68.5%), followed by Facebook (14.1%) and TikTok (10.7%). YouTube and Twitter are rarely used. The second block was used to collect data on the studied variables using Likert scales, where one means "Totally disagree" and five means "Totally agree".

Table 1. Sociodemographic profile of the sample.

	<i>n</i>	%		<i>n</i>	%
Gender			Employment situation		
Female	354	89.7%	Only study	75	19.1%
Male	39	9.8%	Only work	181	45.8%
Non-binary	2	0.5%	Study and work	112	28.4%
			Unemployed	24	6.2%
			Retired	3	0.5%
Age			Social networks		
18–23 years	122	31.0%	Facebook	55	14.1%
24–29 years	159	40.3%	Instagram	270	68.5%
30–35 years	78	19.8%	TikTok	42	10.7%
36–41 years	22	5.5%	Twitter	10	2.6%
42–47 years	8	2.2%	YouTube	9	2.4%
48–53 years	5	1.2%	Other	8	1.7%

3.2. Measurement approach

The construct scales used were previously validated in the literature and adapted to the present study (See Table 2). Since the investigation studied multiple relationships using several latent variables, the observed variables or items were used to measure each construct. A multidimensional scale adapted from (Ohanian, 1990) was used to measure SMI, comprising three dimensions: attractiveness (ATR), trustworthiness (INT), and expertise (EXP). Each dimension consists of two items. EWOM was measured using six items previously proposed by Bambauer-Sachse and Mangold (2011). On the other hand, the Chaudhuri and Holbrook (2001) scale, composed of 4 items, was adapted to evaluate BT. CBE was evaluated using the six-item scale proposed by Hollebeek et al. (2014). Finally, the PI used three items previously applied by Shukla (Shukla, 2011). It is important to acknowledge that, as the scales in previous studies were originally composed in English, they were subsequently translated into Spanish. Prior to the commencement of data collection, a pilot study involving a saturation of 15 samples was conducted to verify the accuracy of the Spanish translations through the use of a back-translation method. The results confirmed no semantic problems in the translation, and the scales correctly measured the proposed variables without any cultural adaptation needed. Finally, a full collinearity approach was conducted to test the common method bias. Since the VIF's values in the inner model were in the range [1.00; 2.48], all below 3.3, the model was considered free of common method bias (Kock, 2015).

3.3. Statistical approach

To respond to the hypotheses, measurement, and structural model estimation, a structural equation model of partial least squares (PLS-SEM) was proposed based on the variance and PLS-SEM algorithm of Lohmöller (2013) (see Figure 1). PLS-SEM was selected because it allows the analysis of relationships between multiple latent variables previously defined as conceptual variables in complex theoretical investigation models (Hair et al., 2011), with many constructs and a large number of indicators (Hair et al., 2012) and because the study aims to maximise the explained variance in the dependent variables rather than confirm a well-established theoretical model (Hair et al., 2017). SmartPLS software was used to calculate the PLS-SEM (Ringle et al., 2015). Five constructs (e—WOM, SMI, CBE, BT, and PI) were conceptualised as reflective (composites in mode A), considering that these constructs and their respective indicators are directly related (Hair et al., 2011). SMI was conceptualised as a reflective-reflective higher-order construct and evaluated using a disjoint two-stage approach, assigning all the low-order components to the higher-order component (Sarstedt et al., 2019). The proposed model was verified in two stages: model measurements and structural testing. The lower-order components were evaluated using loadings and assessed for convergent, internal consistency, reliability, and discriminant validity. The indicators used were λ , α , ρ , ρ_c , AVE, and the heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations HTMT. Because SMI was designed as a reflective-reflective higher-order component, the first phase examined the measurement models of lower-order components. In the second stage, the reflective measurement of SMI was evaluated using the latent variable scores (ATR, INT, and EXP) calculated in the previous stage. A higher-order component measurement evaluation was performed using the same metric as the lower-order components. The structural model was tested using bootstrapping inference statistical analysis with 10.000 resamples. Finally, to evaluate out-of-sample prediction ability, PLS-SEM_{predict} a holdout-sample-based procedure, was estimated using ten folds ($k=10$) and ten repetitions ($r=10$), evaluating first the Q^2_{predict} ; then, considering that the prediction error is highly symmetrically distributed, the root mean squared error (RMSE) was used to compare the PLS-SEM result with the naïve regression linear model (LM) benchmark (Shmueli et al., 2019).

Therefore, because PLS-SEM is designed for linear relationships, the proposed empirical model can be explained using three partial linear regressions as follows:

$$PI = \beta_{EWOM,PI} * EWOM + \beta_{CBE,PI} * CBE + \beta_{SMI,PI} * SMI + \beta_{BT,PI} * BT + \zeta_{PI}$$

$$CEB = \beta_{EWOM,CEB} * EWOM + \beta_{SMI,CEB} * SMI + \zeta_{CEB}$$

$$BT = \beta_{EWOM,BT} * EWOM + \beta_{SMI,BT} * SMI + \zeta_{BT}$$

Table 2. Reliability and validity measures lower and higher-order constructs.

Lower-order construct	Higher-order construct	Indicator	λ	α	ρ	ρ_c	AVE
ATR		ATR1 The Gamarra influencer I follow comes across as attractive.	0.89	0.75	0.75	0.89	0.80
		ATR2 The Gamarra influencer I follow is an elegant person.	0.90				
EXP		EXP1 The Gamarra influencer I follow is a fashion expert.	0.92	0.83	0.83	0.92	0.85
		EXP2 The Gamarra influencer I follow is a qualified person in fashion.	0.93				
INT		INT1 The Gamarra influencer I follow presents herself as a reliable person.	0.94	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.89
		INT2 The Gamarra influencer I follow is a person of integrity.	0.94				
EWOM		EWOM1 I often read online customer reviews of Gamarra products or brands to see which impresses others.	0.85	0.91	0.92	0.93	0.68
		EWOM2 To ensure I buy the correct brand or product, I often read the reviews of other Gamarra customers.	0.90				
		EWOM3 I often refer to other customers' online product reviews to help me choose the right product or brand on Gamarra.	0.91				
		EWOM4 I frequently gather information from online customer reviews of Gamarra before purchasing a product or brand.	0.87				
		EWOM5 I will feel worried before purchasing if I do not read online customer reviews of Gamarra products.	0.69				
		EWOM6 When I buy a product or brand in Gamarra, I trust their customers' online reviews.	0.78				
BT		BT1 I feel that Gamarra generates confidence in me.	0.87	0.92	0.92	0.94	0.81
		BT2 I feel that Gamarra is a good brand.	0.90				
		BT3 I feel that Gamarra is an honest brand.	0.90				
		BT4 I feel that Gamarra is a safe brand.	0.92				
CBE		CBE1 I think a lot of Gamarra when I wear its outfits.	0.74	0.89	0.90	0.92	0.66
		CBE2 Buying outfits in Gamarra makes me curious to discover new brands.	0.77				
		CBE3 I feel safe when I buy outfits in Gamarra.	0.74				
		CBE4 Going to buy outfits in Gamarra makes me feel happy.	0.87				
		CBE5 I feel good when I wear Gamarra outfits.	0.88				
		CBE6 I am proud to wear Gamarra outfits.	0.84				
PI		PI1 I would buy outfits in Gamarra instead of anywhere else.	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.93	0.81
		PI2 I am willing to recommend Gamarra to others.	0.90				
		PI3 When I have to buy outfits in the future, I will visit Gamarra.	0.91				
	SIM	ATR	0.88	0.85	0.85	0.91	0.76
		EXP	0.89				
		INT	0.85				

In the first equation, eWOM, CBE, and SMI explain the dependent variable (PI). In the second and third equations, the independent variables eWOM and SMI are considered to explain CEB and BT, both dependent variables.

4. Results

First, because SIM was evaluated as a higher-order component, following a disjoint two-stage approach, the measurement of the reflective-reflective models of the lower and higher-order components was analysed. In this sense, it was found that all the measures of the lower-order constructs were optimal

Figure 1. Model proposed.

Table 3. Results of discriminant validity analysis—Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT)—lower-order constructs.

	ATR	BT	CBE	EWOM	EXP
ATR					
BT	0.36				
CBE	0.48	0.65			
EWOM	0.43	0.40	0.45		
EXP	0.90	0.39	0.45	0.46	
INT	0.76	0.32	0.47	0.46	0.72
PI	0.29	0.60	0.72	0.27	0.29

Table 4. Results discriminant validity analysis—Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT)—higher-order construct.

	BT	CBE	EWOM	PI
BT				
CBE	0.65			
EWOM	0.40	0.45		
PI	0.60	0.73	0.27	
SMI	0.40	0.52	0.51	0.33

(See Tables 2 and 3) because λ , α , ρ , ρ_c , AVE and the HTMT ratio showed positive results. In the second step, higher-order constructs were measured. As shown in Table 2, all the indicators presented were adequate because all λ values were greater than 0.70 (Jöreskog, 1971). Similarly, the composite reliability offered values of SMI (0.92), EWOM (0.93), BT (0.95), CBE (0.93), and PI (0.93), which reached the minimum expected value of 0.70 (Sarstedt et al., 2021). At the same time, the α values were greater than 0.70, SMI (0.90), eWOM (0.91), BT (0.93), CBE (0.90), and PI (0.89). Moreover, the reliability values ρ_A were between 0.70 and 0.95, representing satisfactory reliability levels (Hair et al., 2017). Similarly, the AVE values were above 0.50, supporting convergent validity (Henseler et al., 2009).

Discriminant validity was calculated for the lower and higher-order constructs. The results shown in Table 3 indicate no discriminant validity problems among the lower-order constructs. Once the reliability of the higher-order models was validated, the discriminant validity was calculated. Accordingly, the discriminant validity was evaluated using the HTMT ratio, obtaining values lower than 0.85 (See Table 4), which validates the different and discriminatory model (Henseler et al., 2015).

The structural model results were assessed once lower- and higher-order reflective model measurements were evaluated. The first step was to assess the lack of collinearity. The structural model's VIF values were calculated (Sarstedt et al., 2021), and the results indicated that all VIF values were below 5; therefore, collinearity was not critical. In the second step, the coefficients of determination were

evaluated. The results of R^2 showed that the model explained 46% of the variance in PI ($R^2=0.46$) and 26% of the variance in CBE ($R^2=0.26$), both of which are considered notable results. In the case of BT ($R^2=0.18$), it explains 18% of the variance, which can be considered low, but it exceeds the minimum value accepted of 0.1 (Falk & Miller, 1992).

Next, bootstrapping with 10,000 resamples (two-tailed test) was performed to test the model hypothesis at significance levels of 0.05 and 0.01 (see Table 5); the path coefficients (β) were also estimated. The results confirmed that hypothesis H1 (EWOM→CBE) was accepted with a β of 0.26; hypothesis H4 (SMI→CBE) was accepted with a β of 0.34, indicating that SMI and EWOM have a positive relationship with CBE. Hypothesis H6 (SMI→BT) was accepted with a β of 0.24, and hypothesis H3 (EWOM→BT) was accepted with a β of 0.26. These results confirm that SMI and EWOM have a positive relationship with BT, even though the path coefficients of both constructs are lower than those with CBE, suggesting that EWOM and SMI are more effective in generating CBE than BT. Hypothesis H7 (BT→PI) was accepted with a β of 0.25, and hypothesis H8 (CBE→PI) was accepted with a β of 0.53, showing that BT and CBE are effective in generating PI, with the results indicating that the strongest relationship is with CBE. Two of the eight hypotheses, H5 (SIM→PI) and H2 (EWOM→PI) were not accepted due to a significance level greater than 0.05. These results suggest that there is no direct relationship between EWOM and SIM in terms of PI. Nevertheless, it is essential to note that although EWOM and SMI do not exhibit a direct relationship with PI, the indirect effects of SMI and EWOM on PI via BT and CBE were calculated using bootstrapping with 10,000 samples, indicating that all four indirect effects were significant, with a p value of 0.01. Even with low path coefficients, the indirect effects are SMI→CBE→PI (0.18), SMI→BT→PI (0.06), EWOM→CBE→PI (0.14), and EWOM→BT→PI (0.07).

The effect of the sample size was evaluated using f^2 . According to Cohen (2013), the effects were medium for the CBE-PI (0.29) and small for the SMI-CBE (0.12), BT-PI (0.07), EWOM-BT (0.07), SMI-BT (0.06), and EWOM-CBE (0.07). In contrast, the results showed that the effect size did not impact SMI-PI (0.00) and EWOM-PI (0.00).

Finally, the predictive power of the model for future observations was assessed using $PLS_{predict}$ following the suggestions of Shmueli et al. (2019). The predictive power of the model was evaluated in two stages. First, $Q^2_{predict}$ was evaluated to confirm that the prediction based on PLS-SEM outperformed the most naïve benchmark (LM). All results of $Q^2_{predict}$ were higher than 0, indicating that the prediction error of the PLS path model was smaller than the prediction error given by the LM (Shmueli et al., 2019). In the second stage, a comparison was made between the PLS-SEM root mean squared error (RMSE) values and the regression linear model (LM). The results showed that all indicators of PLS-SEM had lower values than the naïve LM benchmark, except for CB5, where the RMSE values of PLS-SEM and LM were identical (0.916), and CBE2 and CBE6 had higher PLS-SEM RMSE than LM RMSE. Based on these results, our research model had medium predictive power (Shmueli et al., 2019) (See Table 6).

5. Discussion

This study makes several contributions to cluster and source credibility theories. The first contribution is that, from a theoretical perspective, the results of this investigation confirm the potential of marketing Internet strategies used by a cluster to influence SMEs' sales in an agglomerated economy. This is a remarkable contribution to cluster theory. The results confirm that SMI and eWOM related to a cluster are determinant constructs that generate the cluster's BT and CBE, which finally positively determine the PI of the products the SMEs integrated into the cluster sell.

Table 5. Results of the structural model.

Hypotheses		β	$p < 0.05$	$p < 0.01$	Hypotheses testing	f^2
H1	EWOM → CBE	0.26	0.00	0.00	Yes	0.07
H2	EWOM → PI	-0.05	0.31	0.31	No	0.00
H3	EWOM → BT	0.26	0.00	0.00	Yes	0.07
H4	SMI → CBE	0.34	0.00	0.00	Yes	0.12
H5	SMI → PI	-0.03	0.64	0.64	No	0.00
H6	SMI → BT	0.24	0.00	0.00	Yes	0.06
H7	BT → PI	0.25	0.00	0.00	Yes	0.07
H8	CBE → PI	0.53	0.00	0.00	Yes	0.29

Table 6. PLS_{predict} assessment of manifest variables.

Items	RMSE—PLS-sEM	RMSE—LM	PLS-SEM—LM rMSE	Q ² _{predict}
BT3	0.804	0.818	−0.014	0.130
BT4	0.802	0.813	−0.011	0.135
BT2	0.819	0.834	−0.015	0.129
BT1	0.791	0.800	−0.009	0.152
CBE1	1.094	1.101	−0.007	0.166
CBE5	0.917	0.917	0.000	0.129
CBE2	0.894	0.893	0.001	0.207
CBE6	0.938	0.936	0.002	0.142
CBE4	0.977	0.983	−0.006	0.192
CBE3	0.972	0.988	−0.016	0.134
PI1	0.918	0.929	−0.011	0.049
PI3	0.833	0.834	−0.001	0.092
PI2	0.750	0.757	−0.007	0.059

Furthermore, this research contributes to source credibility theory by confirming that SMI and eWOM, two of the essential variables in Internet marketing strategies where credibility is critical, can contribute to generating positive effects in BT and CBE, not only when those variables are implemented or used by a single company or brand, as previous investigations confirmed, but also when a cluster is the beneficiary of both Internet marketing variables. This finding can be considered critical for cluster theory because, until now, theoretical knowledge about how digital marketing can be helpful to for clustered SMEs has been limited. From the perspective of source credibility theory, the findings suggest that implementing SMI is the most effective strategy at the cluster level, indicating that SMI is apparently more credible than eWOM. This confirms the results of previous investigations, such as those by Van Reijmersdal et al. (2024).

Additionally, this research has found that eWOM, apparently a free-of-charge marketing variable, contributes to the two branding constructs included in the research model, CBE and BT, as Kulkarni et al. (2019) previously confirmed in other contexts, probably because eWOM has the power to change an attitude or preference towards a brand, improve brand experiences, and influence the creation of CBE. Nevertheless, our results suggest that SMI strategies contribute more to a cluster's CBE generation than eWOM. This means there is a strong relationship between the SMI and the predisposition to engage with the brand of the cluster if the influencer posts credible content about the cluster's brand, a finding that reinforces the previous contributions of Tafheem et al. (2021) about these variables. In conclusion, when an influencer posts about a cluster's brand, its followers perceive that the cluster's brand is trustworthy, and the same perception is probably transferred to all unknown brands sold by SMEs integrated into the cluster.

Moreover, the results confirm that neither the cluster SMI nor eWOM directly affects the PI of the products sold by the SMEs agglomerated in the cluster, but they indirectly influence PI through BT and especially CBE. This is a relevant contribution to source credibility theory since, at least at the cluster level, those digital communication constructs are not enough to impulse the PI of potential customers of SMEs, as confirmed by previous investigations (Barbe & Neuburger, 2021). These findings suggest that SMI and eWOM may have the capacity to push people to visit the cluster since the cluster's brand trust can be leveraged to SMEs, but it is not enough to generate the PI in a specific SME. This may be because once customers are in the cluster location, the purchase process starts again, and shoppers choose which SME to buy the products they need in a new dyad relationship. These results confirm that customer behaviour differs when SMI and eWOM promote a cluster or company's brand. At the company level, previous literature has confirmed the usefulness of the SMI dimensions in leading to PI and how an influencer generates in his followers the desire to purchase a specific brand in the future (Woodroof et al., 2020). In the same way, at a single brand level, the previous literature has found that eWOM presents a logical and truthful argument for a positive impact on PI in different contexts (Verma et al., 2023). However, in a cluster, the results confirmed that the cluster's eWOM is not influential in motivating PI in an SME. This is probably because the agglomerated economy comprises thousands of SMEs, each of which has little individual relevance, and clients will choose where to purchase once they are in the cluster.

Nevertheless, this does not mean that both variables are not helpful for the clustered SMEs because, as cluster theory posits, when a cluster collectively implements marketing strategies, it is advantageous

for the SMEs within the cluster (Felzensztein & Deans, 2013). On the contrary, SMI and eWOM are relevant constructs in the process of generating the cluster CBE and BT, variables that directly influence the PI, and even more critically, SMI and eWOM are apparently variables that increase the knowledge about the cluster's brand and impulse customer curiosity to visit the cluster and potentially purchase a product from one of the SMEs confirming in Internet marketing context that consumers also attribute the benefits and strengths of a cluster brand to its individual members as previously did Devigili et al. (2018).

Further, the results have also contributed to understanding the importance of the cluster's CBE and BT in influencing customer behaviour to purchase products from one of the SMEs that join the cluster. More importantly, this research confirmed the relevance of the CBE over the BT in influencing the PI. The results suggest that the cluster's BT is significant in generating buyers' intention to purchase a product from one SME integrated into a cluster, especially if the cluster brand is honest (Alonso Dos Santos et al., 2022) and communicates its authenticity, as Lude & Prüggl, 2018 suggested in their research on BT for SMEs. Even though BT contributes to PI, as von Mettenheim and Wiedmann (2021) confirmed in their study on SMI, the results show how the customer values the clusters' CBE more to motivate PI. In this sense, this study reinforces the previous theoretical contributions regarding the CBE of Bianchi and Andrews (2018), who provide a scope for how CBE affects PI. Nevertheless, our research goes further and confirms that through the interaction in social networks between the cluster's brand and potential customers, cognitive, emotional, and behavioural relationships with the cluster's brand are transferred to the agglomerate of SMEs in the cluster.

Finally, these results are crucial for SMEs that agglomerate into clusters since these findings confirm that Internet marketing strategies to promote a cluster, such as eWOM and SIM, directly or indirectly, contributed to generating and enhancing the sales of SMEs, which is undoubtedly beneficial for those companies that, without the cluster's support, will not have the budget to develop and manage costly marketing strategies, such as SMI, to generate CBE, BT, and PI.

6. Practical implications

Furthermore, in terms of theoretical contributions, this study has practical managerial implications for clusters and SME managers, supported by the empirical results. The findings indicate that for managers of SMEs aiming to maintain relevance in a highly competitive market with constrained marketing budgets, participating in a cluster represents an optimal initial marketing strategy. This is because the cluster's collective brand equity (CBE) and brand trust (BT) are conferred upon all SMEs within the cluster, potentially serving as the initial point of purchase consideration for consumers. Consequently, managers of SMEs within a cluster can optimise their marketing and sales budgets by concentrating efforts on product promotion to capture customer preference once potential customers visit the cluster. The costly branding and communication strategies can be delegated to the cluster, as potential customers initially transfer their trust in the cluster to the SMEs. It is important to note that the cluster's brand will be more effective in ensuring visits to the cluster and gaining customer preference to buy textiles and garments from one of the SMEs than from a department store or commercial centre, but once potential customers are present, each SME can implement its own marketing strategies to be able to sale their products. Second, for cluster managers, the results confirmed the effectiveness of internet marketing strategies in generating clusters CBE and BT. In this sense, the cluster's managers should prioritise their marketing plans to implement SMI and promote eWOM since the cluster brand information generated by the influencers or other customers is essential in the purchasing process of the potential customers of SMEs integrated into the cluster.

Third, since our model has optimal predictive power, if cluster managers need to choose one digital communication strategy between the SMI and eWOM, they should focus on the SMI because a post about the cluster's brand from an influencer is relevant to generating CBE and BT. This is especially important because clusters usually have a limited marketing budget, and investing in the most effective strategies is necessary. Moreover, as the results confirm, Communication brand digital marketing strategies such as eWOM and SMI are not enough to generate a PI from potential customers, and other marketing strategies should probably be implemented at the SME level.

In this sense, the fourth practical implication is that the cluster's brand can promote a customer's PI to one of the thousands of SME economies to agglomerate geographically if those customers trust and/or are engaged with the cluster's brand. For the cluster manager, it means their marketing strategies should be more complex than some previous investigations suggest, since first, they should implement SMI and eWOM marketing campaigns with the objective of improving the cluster BT and CBE; then, through these constructs, in a second phase, they should generate the PI of the product offered by the SMEs. In conclusion, given that the findings indicate cluster CBE is more pertinent to the impulse potential of customer PI, it is imperative for the cluster manager to focus on actively fostering the development of CBE in the short term. Additionally, the manager should devise effective brand strategies that are likely to produce outcomes in the medium to long term. It is important to note that factors beyond SMI or eWOM will be necessary.

7. Conclusions

This study offers significant contributions to both cluster theory and source credibility theory within the realm of digital marketing for clustered SMEs. It confirms that social media influencers (SMI) and electronic word of mouth (eWOM) substantially affect a cluster's brand trust (BT) and customer brand engagement (CBE), which subsequently influence the purchase intention (PI) of products offered by SMEs within the cluster. Notably, while SMI and eWOM do not directly drive PI, their impact is mediated through BT and particularly CBE, highlighting the critical role of the cluster's brand in promoting the products of clustered SMEs.

From a theoretical perspective, the research extends the application of source credibility theory to cluster branding, demonstrating that digital strategies typically employed by individual firms are also effective at the cluster level. It further enriches cluster theory by illustrating that SMI and eWOM can influence the cluster's BT and CBE and that the cluster's brand perception and attitudes can be transferred to the SMEs.

8. Limitations and future research

Despite its theoretical and practical implications, this study has some limitations that need to be considered. From a contextual perspective, the study is limited to a single cluster, raising concerns about the validity of the findings in other contexts. Consequently, future research should be conducted across additional clusters to verify the consistency of the results in diverse contexts where clusters produce and market different types of products to consumers. Furthermore, it would be beneficial to incorporate moderating variables, such as product category, cultural perceptions of influencer authenticity, or the quality of intra-cluster governance, to gain a deeper understanding of the role of the cluster's brand in different contexts. Moreover, it would be interesting to study the triad relationship when cluster SMEs sell their products to other companies in a B2B environment or when the cluster supports international or regional sales of SMEs, as previous investigations did (Devigili et al., 2018; Felzensztein et al., 2012; Felzensztein & Deans, 2013). Furthermore, replicating this study when the cluster SMEs sell services is necessary because, nowadays, the clustering of SME service providers is common (Royo-Vela et al., 2022). Second, since the research was conducted in Peru, other studies are recommended in other regions, as the customer's culture may influence the findings on whether customer attitudes and behaviours about the cluster brand change. In addition to addressing these limitations, future studies should be conducted. To enhance theoretical understanding, it would be beneficial to conduct an in-depth examination of the cluster relationship between SMI and CBE and to propose novel research models that incorporate additional variables, such as cluster brand equity, cluster brand love, or cluster brand attachment. Integrating social media marketing (SMM) into a new research model is appropriate, as electronic word of mouth (eWOM) is occasionally regarded as a dimension of SMM (Sohaib & Han, 2023; Vrontis et al., 2021). Moreover, from a triad perspective, it is essential to know what other customers' attitudes and behaviours towards SMEs would arise related to the cluster's digital and offline marketing strategies; some would be willing to pay a premium price, loyalty, or the SME's financial performance. To conclude, future research must address some methodological considerations. It is essential to recognise that the followers of influencers are integral to the studied population.

The current study did not account for the potential differences in behaviour between the broader customer base of the cluster and the sample. Consequently, future investigations should consider employing diverse data collection methods to capture a more comprehensive range of clients within the cluster. Employing more advanced measurement scales could facilitate a more thorough investigation of the variables outlined in the model. Additionally, qualitative studies involving cluster managers, SME owners, and consumers could offer valuable insights into how the cluster brand affects their attitudes and behaviours.

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Author contributions

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Informed consent statement

Written informed consent was obtained from all the subjects involved in the study.

Institutional review board statement

This research was conducted according to the ethical code for scientific research approved by the Peruvian University of Applied Sciences' ethical committee (INV-COD-01). Peruvian Law to Protect Personal Information. "Ley N° 29733" and the Decreto Supremo N°003-2013-JUS, were considered during this research.

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